

THE DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF PILGRIMAGE TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In this article, in the process of developing pilgrimage tourism in our country, the impact factors of the pandemic on the health of tourism, as well as the role and place of domestic tourism, directions for the development of domestic tourism, and factors affecting the development of the effective use of tourist resources in the regions are described.*

Keywords: *pilgrimage tourism, internal and external tourism, history, pilgrimage sites, cultural sites, pandemic, culture, civilization, economy, ecology, gastronomic tourism, ethnography, history, religion.*

Introduction. Today, large-scale reforms are being implemented in all spheres of social life in Uzbekistan, and the main goal of these reforms is to further develop the country's economy and increase the welfare of the Uzbek people. The tourism sector occupies a special place in one of the main centers of these reforms. Therefore, pilgrimage tourism, which plays an important role in the economic development and growth of Uzbekistan, in recent years, as well as other sectors of the tourism industry, great attention is being paid to the development of pilgrimage tourism in the country. Nowadays, interest in the study of temples and shrines is growing in the world, because holy places are an integral part of people's daily life. With the active participation of world brands, we should pay special attention to the development of tourism, environmental education, ethnographic, gastronomic, tourism and other areas in this sector. In this regard, we should take into account that the use of public-private partnerships opens wide opportunities for the development of the sector. It is also possible to pave the way for the development of this industry by developing the "Little Trip" program, which consists of visiting the holy places and monuments in the ancient and historical cities of our country - Samarkand, Bukhara, Khorezm, Surkhandarya and Tashkent. Also, it is necessary to fully implement large-scale opportunities in the field of domestic tourism. In particular, we found it permissible to bring to your attention below the most famous and beautiful shrines in our beloved country about their brief history and culture. Including

1. Zangi ota mausoleum

This mausoleum, located in a town near Tashkent, was built by order of Amir Temur. Zangi ota (Father) was one of the great thinkers and mystic sages of the Turko-Islamic world. Zangi ota was also known by the nickname Himmatiy. He was a dark-skinned, chubby (camel-lipped), strong, well-built man. His wife Anbar Ana is also buried here. The mausoleum complex consists of several zones: a large garden and a mosque, a madrasah, a minaret, and an Anbar mother mausoleum built in the 14th-19th centuries. In 1914-1915, a minaret was built in front of the mosque. In 2013, works on the expansion of the garden and the Prayer Mosque were carried out, increasing the attractiveness of the shrine.

2. "Zirkmozor" shrine

Zirkmozor shrine is located in the village of Arbagish, Chortoq district, Namangan region, and is considered one of the holy places. Among the people, there are different legends about this

place, like other shrines. It is said that our Prophet Muhammad Mustafa (sav) bequeathed his precious robes to Sultan Voiz before his death. They bequeathed it to their relatives to hand it over to the owner. After their death, Hazrat Ali, the son-in-law of our Prophet, was entrusted with the task of handing over this robe to Sultan Voiz. Hazrat Ali Sultan came to Zikrmazor in search of the preacher and prayed there. It is said that a tree came out of the place where Hazrat Ali rested his head while praying, and a spring came out of the place where he stuck his staff. Therefore, this place has been turned into a pilgrimage site based on the legends that it is considered a sacred place where the steps of Hazrat Ali reached.

3. Kirq Kiz fortress

Kirq Kiz fortress was discovered in the Khorezm region in 1938, 30 km north of the city of Beruni. According to scientists, the castle belongs to the 1st-6th centuries AD. Zoroastrian graves were found during excavations. According to one of the legends, a princess named Guloyim lived in this fortress, and she and her forty comrades defended the border and protected it from the attacks of their opponents. To this day, the outer walls with fortification holes have been preserved.

4. Pottery workshops in Rishton

Rishton in the Fergana Valley has long been considered the home of excellent pottery. In Rishton, a special technology for creating ceramic products, their firing and glazing has been developed. At the moment, more than 1000 potters are working in Rishton, about 100 of them know all the technologies of pottery art. The products created by Rishton masters are included in the collections of many museums around the world.

5. Varakhsha shrine

If you go to Bukhara, be sure to visit Varakhsha - the ancient city where the residence of the Bukhara rulers ruled Bukhara until the Arab conquest. Varakhsha is located in the west of Bukhara, half an hour's drive away, and covers an area of 100 hectares. The study of the frescoes of the Varakhsha Palace showed that the city existed from the 5th century to the 11th century AD. Scientists believe that life in Varakhsha came to a standstill due to the lack of water in the region. Once upon a time, this place was equal to Bukhara. Today, Varakhsha is a ruin, looking at it naturally evokes thoughts about the distant past.

6. Bukhara. Directions of 7 holies

Bukhara is the homeland of seven great Sufis of the Naqshbandi sect. The great representatives of Sufism lived here, engaged in religious and social activities, and contributed to the creation and prosperity of blessed Bukhara, spiritual education, and the elevation of emotional spirit. The burial places of holy Sufis - pyres and Islamic shrines have been preserved here.

Most of the pilgrims to Bukhara start their journey by visiting the mausoleum of Khodja Abdulkholiq Gijduvani, the spiritual teacher who founded the Naqshbandi doctrine. Abdulkholiq Gijduvani is related to the tenth generation of our Prophet. The ten pillars and supports of the mausoleum porch refer to the tenth generation. During the reign of Khodja Abdulkholiq Gijduvani, the mausoleum served as a cooling house, where people came to pray during the forty-day heat wave. Over time, the holy place of worship will become a place of honor.

7. Samarkand. Complex of Bukhari

Imam al-Bukhari, one of the famous scholars of the Muslim world, 810 years.

He was born on July 21 in Bukhara, died in 870 in the village of Khartang, located 25 km from Samarkand (now Chelak district of Samarkand region), and was buried there. However, the place had been neglected for centuries. After the independence of Uzbekistan, the complex was

restored. On April 29, 1997, the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan decided to celebrate the 1225th anniversary of Imam al-Bukhari's birthday according to the Hijri lunar calendar. In November of this year, the general conference of UNESCO will decide to participate in the celebration of the 1225th anniversary of the birth of the scientist Ismail al-Bukhari in 1998. In this regard, in the mausoleum of Imam al-Bukhari Middle

A memorial complex was built according to Asian architectural traditions. The total area of land allocated for the monument is 10 hectares. The complex connects to the Samarkand Imam al-Bukhari highway.

8. Open-air museum

Khiva is one of the oldest cities rich in historical monuments not only in Uzbekistan, but also in Central Asia. Information about the city dates back to the 6th century BC. It was the center of Khiva Khanate until 1920. The main part of the architectural monuments of the city, which was historically divided into two castles, is located in Ichan Castle. Muhammad Aminkhan Madrasah, Kaltaminor, Taskhovli Palace, Olloqli Khan Madrasah and other buildings are noteworthy.

9. Nurota fountainhead

Nurota is one of the ancient cities of Uzbekistan. The city was first mentioned in Narshahi's History of Bukhara in the 10th century as Nur (after the famous Nur spring here). The appearance of the city in local legends dates back to the time of Alexander the Great. Later, the city was called Nurota in honor of the famous Sheikh Abulhasan Nuri (XII century) who lived here. A branch of the Great Silk Road passed over Nurota. In the past, it had military-strategic importance and was considered a major trade center.

In conclusion, we should emphasize that Uzbekistan is a place of pilgrimage not only for Islam, but also for many other religions. Based on this, it can be said that the importance of developing the tourism industry and determining the future prospects of pilgrimage tourism in our country is very high. Uzbekistan and the countries of the world united, there is a need to popularize not only the needs of the current people, but also the tourism culture of future generations, in particular, to further strengthen the attitude to pilgrimage tourism through the development of general tourism projects.

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